

PAINTING

THE ARTISTIC LANGUAGE OF CHINESE WATERCOLOR IN ORIENTAL CICONIA BOYCIANA PAINTINGS

Wencui Zhang

Cross-Cultural, Kookmin University, South Korea.
ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-2315-9850>
Email: cherry1001kookmin.ac.kr

Dongkwon Seong*

Cross-Cultural, Kookmin University, South Korea.
ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7607-1572>
Email: dongkwonseong@kookmin.ac.kr

ABSTRACT

Background: Watercolor, originating in eighteenth-century Britain, entered China via cultural exchange and absorbed traditional Chinese visual language. Practice shifted from Western emulation to national identity, forming a distinctly Eastern watercolor that now engages ecological discourse; the Class-I protected Oriental stork (*Ciconia boyciana*) indicates wetland health. **Objective:** Assess how localized Chinese watercolor—via the Yellow River Delta and portrayals of the Oriental stork—adds visual and cultural value to ecological narratives and public awareness. **Methods:** Conduct a historical-aesthetic review of watercolor’s localization; a Yellow River Delta case study integrating Eastern and Western principles; visual analysis of works depicting *Ciconia boyciana*; and appraisal of communicative capacity in ecological storytelling. **Results:** Chinese watercolor fuses Eastern and Western aesthetics, broadening expression for nuanced depictions of wetlands and species vulnerability. Portrayals of the Oriental stork foreground symbolic and ecological meanings, linking cultural identity with habitat health and serving as accessible narratives that elevate attention to biodiversity and conservation. **Conclusions:** By synthesizing aesthetic traditions, Chinese watercolor has evolved into a medium well-suited to ecological communication. Artistic interventions—particularly those focused on emblematic species and sensitive habitats—can effectively raise awareness of biodiversity and sustainable development while reinforcing a distinctly Eastern visual identity.

KEY WORDS

Watercolor Painting, Chinese Watercolor, Ecological Conservation, Oriental *Ciconia Boyciana*, Composition, Color.

INTRODUCTION

The term “watercolor painting” is defined in dictionaries as “painting produced by mixing pigments with water” in which various pigments are dispersed or dissolved in water to execute the work (Park, 2017). Western watercolor painting can be traced to eighteenth-century Britain, where it was initially employed to depict geological formations and landscapes for the aristocratic class and was characterized by a narrative quality. The medium was introduced to China during the late Ming period as Western learning spread eastward, and a cohort of returning students who integrated Western artistic methods with traditional cultural art began to develop the localized characteristics of Chinese watercolor painting (Chee, 2025). After various explorations, this new art form began to take root and sprout, culminating in the opening of the Tushanwan Painting Museum in Shanghai in 1864. The increased value of art in China, driven by modern educational progress, fueled the development of Chinese watercolor painting as a tradition with distinct Chinese characteristics that integrated national temperament and aesthetic taste and was deeply influenced by the rich heritage of Chinese local culture (Meng, 2020).

Growing recognition of the distinctive national style of Chinese watercolor painting has motivated scholarly research into its developmental trajectory, expressive techniques, and cultural connotations. Existing studies primarily examine Sino-Western technique integration pathways, the cultivation of national characteristics in Chinese watercolor painting, and the current development status and market value of the medium.

Focusing on technique integration, Liang investigates “how watercolor art can draw sustenance from Chinese painting techniques and aesthetic philosophies” (Liang, 2022), and Wang explores the theoretical implications and practical benefits of incorporating the time-honored brushwork techniques of classical ink painting into the ethnicization of watercolor painting (Wang, 2017). Regarding the shaping of national characteristics, Li asserts that “Chinese watercolor painting possesses a unique artistic temperament and is rich in humanistic values reflective of its national identity” (Li, 2018).

Meanwhile, Yuan points out that after Western watercolor painting was introduced to China, it absorbed aspects of China’s profound and extensive traditional culture, gradually coalescing into a unique genre with Chinese national temperament and artistic taste (Yuan, 2009). In a similar vein, Chen argues that Chinese watercolor

paintings, with their unique artistic language, carry the profound spiritual core of the Chinese nation, not only possessing a distinct oriental charm in expressive forms and aesthetic tastes but also resonating with the emotions and values of the Chinese people at the spiritual connotation level, highlighting specific characteristics of China’s national culture (Chen, 2023).

Finally, in terms of development status and market value, Zhang analyzes the “current status and underlying causes of watercolor painting’s development, identifies emerging issues, and proposes corresponding solutions” (Zhang, 2017). Relatedly, Minglu and Albattat provide an overview of the current state of Chinese watercolor artists and the commercial intermediaries in the Chinese watercolor art industry, offering insights into the development of China’s watercolor art market (Minglu & Albattat, 2023), and Minglu, Albattat and Azman (2023) examine how the market environment for watercolor painting in China moderates the relationship between the current state of the domestic watercolor painting market and its prospective development.

Although the above studies provide theoretical support for the creative practice of Chinese watercolor painting and lay a solid foundation for further development of contemporary watercolor art, research in the field remains predominantly theoretical and focused on macro-level trend analyses, leaving ample room for micro-level empirical studies on thematic innovation and technical interchangeability in specific creative practices. This paper aims to broaden the scope of research into Chinese watercolor painting by analyzing painting themes, considering the interconnections between Chinese painting and watercolor painting, and applying theoretical techniques of traditional Chinese painting to one’s own watercolor art practice.

In recent years, the continuous deterioration of the global ecological environment has rendered the protection of endangered species increasingly urgent. The Yellow River Delta, one of China’s most significant wetland ecosystems, is home to numerous rare migratory bird species, including the *Ciconia boyciana*. However, human activities and climate change now severely threaten the ecological environment of the Yellow River Delta. As a Class-I nationally protected species, the survival status of *Ciconia boyciana* reflects both habitat health and the overall stability of the wetland ecosystem.

The *Ciconia boyciana* (Figure 1) is a large wading bird belonging to the Ciconiiformes

order, Ciconiidae family (Hancock, 1992). A Class-I nationally protected bird, it is listed as EN (Endangered) on the IUCN (The International Union for Conservation of Nature) Red List (BirdLife International, 2018). It is endemic to East Asia, primarily breeding in the Russian Far East and Northeast China and wintering mainly in eastern and southeastern China and, more limitedly, in Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan. It typically inhabits wetlands such as marshes, rivers, lakes, ponds, and canals (Figure 2) (Garidi et al., 2022). As a Class-I protected species, the *Ciconia boyciana* is safeguarded not only for its rarity but also for its profound auspicious symbolism in Chinese culture. The *Ciconia boyciana* is considered one of the most auspicious of birds. While making sacrifices to Heaven, Emperor

Wu purportedly saw a flock of white cranes and subsequently issued a special edict recognizing white cranes as sacred beings sent down by Heaven (Ban & Shi, 2012).

Figure 1: *Ciconia Boyciana*.

Figure 2: Habitat of the Oriental *Ciconia Boyciana* (*Ciconia boyciana*).

Artistic creators use visual language to intervene in the real world and can leverage their artistic work to evoke public awareness of ecological conservation and enhance societal attention to endangered species. Therefore, this paper analyzes ecologically themed watercolor art, focusing on the Oriental *Ciconia boyciana* as a subject of artistic creation and the role and value of watercolor painting in ecological conservation, seeking to highlight the sensitivity of artistic language to natural life and its ability to achieve a deep fusion of art, nature, culture, and life in an ecological aesthetics framework.

ARTISTIC EXPRESSION IN CHINESE WATERCOLOR

The Ontological Language of Watercolor Fusion of Water and Pigment

The beauty of watercolor art lies in the serendipitous interaction between water and pigment, embodying the element of chance in artistic creation. This interplay gives the medium its uniquely fluid and permeative aesthetic, making it a highly expressive means of conveying emotional flux.

Transparency is an intrinsic property of water.

Similarly, the water solubility of watercolor pigments gives them an inherent translucency. The transparency of water combined with the dissolved watercolor pigments synergistically elevates the two natural translucencies—combining pigment clarity with the dynamism of water to establish the medium’s gentle tonal foundation. After blending with water, watercolor pigments develop progressive layers while retaining their underlying hue, giving the medium its characteristic transparency.

The use of water as the vehicle for pigment—a choice that endows it with its characteristic luminosity and fluidity—distinguishes watercolor from other Western painting media. Unlike oil or acrylic—which are typically worked on easels or even laid flat for impasto effects—watercolor is almost invariably applied to a horizontal plane, allowing the pigments to mingle with the paper’s unpainted areas and each other in a uniquely spontaneous manner (Luo, 2020). In watercolor painting, variations in water fluidity can elicit distinct emotional responses in viewers. Artists should strategically harness the aqueous qualities inherent in their decorative visual vocabularies to imbue compositions with emotionally undulating

effects, thereby fully revealing the dynamic aesthetic potential of watercolor art. In Figure 3, the flat-wash technique maintains color uniformity and surface evenness through even pigment application, resulting in a calm, stable visual impression. Conversely, the graded wash exploits the pigment's natural diffusion on the water's

surface to produce a transition from intense to pale and from dense to light, endowing the composition with rhythmic beauty and a sense of cadence. This chromatic gradient both enhances spatial depth and embodies the gradual progression and release of emotion, vividly illustrating watercolor's expressive qualities of "fluidity" and "transparency."

FLAT WASH

Paint the area with plain water.

Apply color evenly, allowing it to spread across the wet paper.

Avoid interfering with the wash, so that it maintains the flat appearance as it dries.

GRADATED WASH

Paint the area with plain water.

Apply a heavy amount of pigment to the brush, and place it at the edge of the wet area of paper.

Allow the paint to gradually spread through the wet area so that the color is dark on one side and gets lighter as it spreads.

Figure 3: Two Modes of Water–Pigment Fusion in Watercolor.

Dry–Wet Techniques

Dry-wet techniques are among the most commonly employed methods in the creation of watercolor paintings. "The dry technique is defined as employing pigments with minimal water, which may be executed as a single flat wash or through multiple overlapping layers" (Gardner, 1975). For example, Frank Eber's watercolor *Boat* (Figure 4) exemplifies this method: the composition is rich and decorative, displaying a distinctive personal style. Eber utilizes simple geometric forms to convey the scene's atmosphere and emotional tenor. The outlines of the boats, buildings, and figures are clear, with sharp boundaries and pronounced brushstrokes, yielding an uneven textural quality reminiscent of the "dry-brush" effect, where low brush moisture produces granular pigment deposits on paper. The red and blue hull color blocks appear saturated without excessive diffusion, indicating that Eber applied relatively dry pigment directly rather

than allowing water to spread naturally.

Figure 4: Frank Eber, *Boat* (paper, watercolor).

The wet-on-wet wash is a classical watercolor method in which pigment is applied to a pre-

moistened surface, allowing colors to merge organically. Practically, the artist first saturates the targeted paper area with clean water and then introduces pigment, yielding soft-edged forms that flow and diffuse within the dampened region. This method vividly exemplifies the fundamental transparency and fluidity inherent to watercolor media (Xing, 2017).

For example, Italian artist Giorgio Morandi's two watercolor still lifes (Figure 5) exemplify the wet technique, one of his signature methods. In these

works, color boundaries blur and interpenetrate one another, particularly at the junctions between bottles, jars, and background, where edges exhibit a soft, diffused effect. The natural transitions afforded by the wet technique impart a light, airy visual effect. Morandi's chromatic palette leans toward low-saturation gray-brown, pale blue, and soft purple hues; this scheme relies heavily on the wet technique to facilitate color interpenetration, avoid hard edges, and engender a sense of spatial fluidity.

Figure 5 Work a (14 × 24 cm, 1959)

Figure 5 Work b (21×30cm 1959)

Figure 5: Giorgio Morandi, Still Life (paper, watercolor).

In practice, artists seldom employ a single, unadulterated technique; instead, dry- and wet-brush methods are integrated or alternated to harness their complementary virtues. Juxtapositions of coarse and fine, sparse and dense, and loose and tight strokes generate heightened aesthetic tension and dynamic visual impact (Si, 2018).

Diverse Manifestations of Chinese-Painting Elements in Watercolor Pen-and-Ink Language

Ink tonality is a crucial visual element in Chinese ink painting; the fusion of ink and color—with color residing in the ink and vice versa—epitomizes the tradition. On this basis, Chinese watercolor painting cleverly integrates the concept of blank space, water control, and stroke transformation of Chinese painting. Through precise management of the relationship between reality and virtuality in paintings, subtle control of watercolor blending, and innovative interpretation of traditional brushwork, it both maintains the implicit charm of Eastern aesthetics and highlights the unique expressive power of watercolor art. One similarity between Chinese painting and watercolor is the use of unpainted, white areas in compositions.

In watercolor, the unpainted areas can balance compositions and highlight images. In addition, they provide viewers space to engage in imaginative projection. In this sense, viewers can “finish” the paintings (Zhen, 2011). Watercolor artists strictly control the dilution and concentration of pigments according to the requirements of Chinese painting for ink intensity, moisture, and dryness, aiming to create rich layers and textures. At the same time, they inherit and expand the brushstroke techniques of Chinese painting, such as lifting, pressing, jerking, center, and side, fully utilizing the fluidity and permeability of watercolor media to enhance the tension and rhythm in their work. In this way, between reality and virtuality, watercolor and ink blend and reflect each other, not only creating profound, three-dimensional spatial effects, but also showcasing the innovative continuation of the Eastern aesthetic spirit in modern watercolor art.

In the development of contemporary watercolor art, Huang Tieshan's works typify the fusion of Chinese painting and Western watercolor techniques. Huang Tieshan is skilled particularly skilled at combining the fluidity and transparency of watercolor with the expressive “freehand” (*xie yi*) and “blank space” (*liu bai*) of Chinese painting

to create works that are both ethereal and full of tension. Similarly, Guan Guangzhi, regarded as a founding figure of modern Chinese watercolor painting, exemplifies the integration of Chinese painting language within watercolor's diverse expressive modes. Combining traditional Chinese compositional principles and the spirit of brush and ink with Western watercolor material properties, he has pioneered a watercolor expression system with distinct Eastern aesthetic qualities, becoming a

key catalyst for the localization and diversification of Chinese watercolor. His establishment of the "retained-color fill-void" (liuse tiankong) fill-in-the-blank method also draws upon Chinese painting's color application concepts to effect a localized innovation in watercolor technique. Table 1 summarizes the distilled Chinese painting elements manifested in the watercolor works of the two artists.

Table 1: Work Analysis.

Artist	Work Title	Blank-Space Consciousness	Water Control	Brushwork Transitions
Huang Tieshan	 "Hometown Series: Ancient Village"	Tieshan employs blank space as negative form through "reserve by staining" (ran liubai), "reserve by support" (tuo bai), and "reserve by lifting" (ti bai) layers--techniques that not only reinforce the gradations of mist and light, but introduce rhythmic tension via contrasts of solid and void lines, thereby expanding the emotional and imaginative scope of the scene.	In the background, Tieshan applies a "more water, less pigment" thin wash while using a "less water, more pigment" rich wash in the foreground; he combines semi-dry timing switches, layered drying, and flow guidance to precisely balance wet-dry rhythm, achieving both transparent gradation and structural clarity.	Tieshan initially lays a wet sweep, then switches to a dry-brush "break wash" at semi-dry stage; he transitions from broad strokes to fine linework, from side-tip to center-tip, with lifting to a fine point and pausing to concentrate ink, completing an organic transformation of solidity/void, thickness/fineness, and rhythmic pacing.
Guan Guangzhi	 "Fragrant Hills Glazed Pagoda"	At the junction of pagoda, sky, and foliage, Guangzhi retains extensive liubai as negative form, accentuating the pagoda's transparency and establishing solid-void rhythm; he overlays "supporting liubai" and ultra-dilute color layers, using with "lifting liubai" to dot edges subtly, thereby enhancing visual depth and rhythmic harmony.	In localized dark areas, Guangzhi first performs "color anchoring" by letting highly concentrated pigment rest in place to create dense pigment clusters; once semi-dry, he applies a "drag wash"—using clear water or low-concentration color pulled along edges—to produce soft gradations, thereby augmenting luminosity and atmosphere.	Guangzhi uses side-tip, loose wet stroke to establish a soft sky and foliage ambiance, then employs a center-tip, tightly gripped dry brush to delineate the pagoda's structure; he flexibly alternates light lifts and press-pauses to achieve coordinated contrasts of solid/void, loose/tight, and thickness/fineness.

Aesthetic Concepts

During its development, Chinese watercolor painting has both drawn on the media and techniques of traditional Chinese painting and served as a means of transmitting national culture and the art of visual language. Every ethnic art tradition possesses conventions and characteristics that are closely linked to the culture and social context of its people. The national characteristics of ancient Chinese art theory include the influence of Daoist cultural thought. Laozi, the founder of Daoism, asserted that "the Dao follows nature" (Laozi, 2021), thus positioning Daoism as a practice modeled on and drawing inspiration from the natural world. In traditional Chinese painting, the principle of "Learning from Nature and Feeling from Heart" instructs artists to regard the natural world as their primary creative mentor, encouraging them to extract its aesthetic essence, integrate this essence with their own internal inspiration, and thereby achieve an artistic process that organically unifies the two (Quan, 2023). In addition, Laozi proposed the idea of "governance through non-action" (Laozi, 2021). The concept of "non-action" denotes complete alignment with natural laws and proscribes the pursuit of objectives outside those laws, positing that, paradoxically, this very alignment enables those who achieve it

to accomplish all their intended ends. This state of purposive purposelessness—or purposeless purpose—constitutes a supra-utilitarian aesthetic realm. Chinese painters employ imagination to render expressive interpretations of nature, adhering to the Daoist philosophy of unity between humanity and the cosmos in pursuit of harmony with the natural world. This reverence for the spirit of nature elevates watercolor works beyond mere depiction of objective scenes, ascending to expressions of natural vitality and deeper connotation. For example, contemporary masters such as Huang Tieshan champion the "return to nature," depicting their native landscapes to convey a love for land and life and aiming to evoke in viewers a sense of awe and affection for the natural world.

The interplay of void and solidity constitutes a distinctive artistic method in ancient Chinese art theory. This concept is derived from Daoist notions of the Dao–phenomena relationship and being–nonbeing, emphasizing their union with priority given to void to maximize its expressive function. Unlike Western oil painting, Chinese painting backgrounds are often left deliberately unfilled, using void to accentuate solidity and thereby express the infinite through the finite and provide

viewers with an evocative, open-ended aesthetic space. Chinese watercolor painters likewise seek to embody the principle of void–solid integration.

Contemporary watercolor practice in China emphasizes the cultivation of an Eastern sensibility—one defined by restraint, ethereality, and an evocative meaning that transcends mere representation. Practitioners often draw upon the brush vitality and strategic use of negative space inherited from ink painting, pursuing “spiritual resonance” (*qi yun*) and a poetic mode of expression. This orientation toward atmosphere and symbolism has become a distinguishing hallmark of Chinese watercolor, setting it apart from Western methodologies (Wang et al., 2024). Moreover, Zhuangzi’s emphasis on meaning over words influences both the “spiritual resonance” in these works and Gu Kaizhi’s “portray spirit through form” (*yi xing chuan shen*) principle from the Six Dynasties.

Ancient Chinese artistic creation—whether in literature, painting, calligraphy, poetry, or music—placed great emphasis on the creation of “artistic conception” (*yi jing*). Artistic conception is exemplified by a series of traditional methods—“meaning beyond words,” “spirit transmission,” “void–solid integration,” and “integration of emotion and scene”—which collectively define the process of shaping artistic imagery.

Artists, through light washes and compositions that juxtapose void and solidity, evoke an Eastern poetic realm, eliciting an emotional resonance that transcends mere representation. Wu Guanzhong’s artistic philosophy embodies this principle; he emphasized that painting should possess both “formal beauty” and “spirit transmission” and valued the expression of subjective aesthetic interest, incorporating calligraphic lines and rhythms into his landscape painting (Figure 6) (Christie’s, 2025), using concise brushstrokes to capture the charm of the scenery, and achieving unity of form and spirit.

Figure 6: Wu Guanzhong, “Grand Canyon” (paper, watercolor).

In the context of globalization, contemporary Chinese watercolorists have maintained cultural self-awareness by rigorously sustaining their indigenous artistic ethos, even as they actively participate in the international art milieu to foster dialogue and synthesis between Eastern and Western aesthetic traditions. From the twentieth century onward, these practitioners have undergone a conceptual evolution—shifting from an initial paradigm of “learning from the West” to one that foregrounds and asserts a distinctly national artistic stance (Zang, 2024). This shift has diversified Chinese watercolor in theme and style, expanding subject matter from traditional landscapes to contemporary urban scenes and leading painters to address humanistic concerns and global themes. Chinese watercolor artists have employed realistic techniques to depict Chinese subjects and used light-and-shadow techniques to infuse national spirit into figurative imagery to allow overseas audiences to experience the essence of Eastern aesthetics, thereby propelling Chinese watercolor’s achievements and concepts onto the global stage.

The aesthetic concepts of contemporary Chinese watercolor painting have continually developed at the intersection of tradition and modernity and between Eastern and Western cultures. The notions of natural spirit and Eastern ambiance have endowed watercolor painting with profound humanistic depth, while cultural self-awareness and a global perspective have expanded its thematic scope and aesthetic framework. Overall, contemporary Chinese watercolor painting showcases an impressive and diverse level of aesthetic integration: it not only values the inherent spirit of Chinese painting’s “lively spirit and charm” (*qiyun shengdong*), but also boldly absorbs the formal beauty and technical innovation of Western painting, ultimately forming a contemporary watercolor art style with both national characteristics and international perspectives. The formation and practice of these aesthetic concepts have both elevated the academic status of watercolor in the Chinese art community and contributed new insights and perspectives to the development of global watercolor art.

EMOTIONAL EXPRESSION IN WATERCOLOR CREATION

Composition Methods

Referring to the manner in which artists arrange and organize visual elements on the pictorial plane, composition determines the structure, balance, and visual impact of artistic works and substantially influences expressive power and viewer engagement. The importance of composition

manifests in its capacity to convey the artist’s creative intent and emotional expression. Chinese watercolor artists frequently employ composition strategies such as void–solid integration, S-shaped flow, circular framing, and diagonal layouts, through which inner emotion and aesthetic meaning are communicated via interwoven rhythms and contrasts of depth and void (Table 2).

Void—Solid Integration

Composition theory in watercolor addresses layout, visual center of gravity, and equilibrium, paralleling Chinese painting principles of “alternating void and solid” and “blank space.” Contemporary watercolorists use strategic blank areas and void–solid treatment to create imaginative space and atmospheric depth, thereby enhancing layering and spatial perception and guiding emotional resonance. As Tianshou Pan observed, “Western painting emphasizes chiaroscuro to define form, whereas Chinese painting employs blank space and lines, varying density only slightly between primary and secondary areas to achieve tonal modulation” (Pan, 2017).

S–Curve Composition

This method is characterized by a fluid, gentle, and expansive visual quality, guiding the viewer’s gaze in a natural rhythmic flow. It also embodies dialectical thought, epitomized by the Daoist Taiji diagram. As the Zhouyi Benyi states, “There is Taiji in Yi, from which the Two Modes arise: Taiji is the Dao; the Two Modes are Yin and Yang; Yin and Yang are one” (Zhouyi Benyi, qtd. in Zhu, 2010).

The Taiji’s “double-fish” motif, with its S-shaped rotation and seamless union and separation, illustrates the visual-aesthetic basis of Chinese compositional harmony.

Circular Composition

Psychologically, circular framing conveys rotation, movement, and contraction, and is widely adopted in watercolor to evoke softness, completeness, and serene harmony, characterized by a pronounced sense of mass. Circular viewing windows effectively guide the observer’s gaze toward the visual center, leveraging innate spatial-psychological effects to create aesthetic appeal.

Diagonal Composition

Although originally aimed at photographers, Westhoff’s “Diagonal Method” is explicitly transferable to watercolor painting: “placing focal elements along 45° lines to generate a more engaging, dynamic composition” (Westhoff, 2009). Diagonal composition not only highlights the main subject of the picture, but also gives the picture a stronger sense of hierarchy and extensibility, allowing the viewer’s gaze to naturally move along the diagonal axis, thereby enhancing the dynamic feeling of the picture.

Others

Beyond these, watercolor composition also encompasses central, longitudinal, symmetrical, and balanced formats. Artists do not adhere to rigid patterns but integrate and innovate flexibly, reconfiguring time, space, and imagery to create new possibilities for the medium.

Table 2: Composition Forms in Watercolor and Selected Works.

Composition Form	Artist & Work	Analysis
Void–solid integration	 Sarfraz Musavir (Pakistan), Watercolor Work	Western realist technique and Eastern expressive spirit are fused to convey both presence and veracity through areas of void. Localized blank spaces accentuate chiaroscuro, afford viewers expanded imaginative space, and provoke deeper reflection and emotional resonance.
S-curve composition	 David Hockney, Nichols Canyon (1980)	A winding road traces an S-curve that injects dynamism, while surrounding houses, trees, and mountains establish a stable frame, balancing motion and stillness. Non-traditional perspective lets the road bend freely, heightening the subjective viewpoint and narrative vitality.
Circular composition	 Keith Anden Achepohl, Tondo VII (1984)	Presented within a perfect circle, the ringed edge directs the eye back toward the center, creating a continuous flow of color and brushwork. This cyclical movement reinforces focus and delivers a harmonious, rhythmic viewing experience.

Composition Form	Artist & Work	Analysis
Diagonal composition	 Joseph Mallord William Turner, Falls of the Rhine at Schaffhausen, Front View (1841)	The waterfall cascades along a diagonal axis from upper right to lower left, driving the spatial rhythm. Loose, wet washes and scraped highlights balance the sense of flowing water with an airy atmosphere, enhancing both dynamism and spatial depth.

Color Application

In watercolor creation, theoretical approaches to color application primarily encompass color layering, gradation, and saturation control. At its core, watercolor's expressive power derives from the balance between water and pigment: water shapes tone and mood, while pigment defines color intensity and atmosphere. By adjusting the ratios between them, artists unlock a spectrum of effects—from light, translucent washes to deep, richly saturated passages, and from minimalist restraint to lush opulence—thus harnessing the medium's unique capacity for evocative, mood-driven imagery (Wang, 2023).

At present, color tends to be linked to human society, used to express the social and cultural attributes of humanity. Contemporary Chinese watercolorists have cast off the limitations of Western realist color systems, privileging subjective perception and emotional resonance over strict fidelity to appearance. By foregrounding inner experience rather than replication, their work achieves a heightened expressiveness and emotional intensity that reflects the artist's personal vision (Quan, 2023). Painters can express specific emotions or themes through variations in color and form, a mode of expression referred to as "imagery," whose underlying connotations and emotional depth constitute "artistic implication". Artists utilize warm and cool hues, light-dark contrasts, and chromatic juxtaposition to evoke distinct emotions and atmospheres.

For example, cool palettes can convey tranquility or detachment, whereas warm palettes express passion and excitement. Tonal value also conveys emotion: bright colors can communicate joy and positivity, while muted tones can express melancholy and calm. Artists use harmonious or contrasting color pairings to articulate a range of emotional states.

In watercolor, color is the primary vehicle for conveying depth and mood. Tonal gradations and warm-cool contrasts signal spatial recession, while simultaneously enriching chiaroscuro and tactile presence. Artists typically render distant planes in light, muted washes and fine lines to

create atmospheric haze, reserving saturated hues and vigorous strokes for the foreground to assert weight and texture. This chromatic progression naturally steers the viewer's gaze from near to far, expanding the illusion of three-dimensional space.

In practice, color must harmonize with the overall composition while addressing local detail. Chiaroscuro treatment is intimately tied to color, as light-dark contrasts can underscore form and infuse painted work with vitality. The dynamic interplay of color, line, and light generates a rich layering effect, lending watercolor works greater expressiveness and visual impact.

In *Spring River Warms* (Figure 7), color functions as the primary vehicle for emotion and atmosphere. A soft green palette conveys spring's vitality, with the warm accents on the ducks expressing affection. Tonal shifts and line variation articulate the water's play of light and shadow. The painting not only depicts the beauty of spring but also communicates reverence for nature, urging humanity to coexist in harmony with the natural world.

Figure 7: Wang Xuetao, *Spring River Warms*.

COMPOSITION DESIGN

Conceptualization of the Work

Despite widespread recognition of the critical role they play in climate regulation, water purification, and biodiversity maintenance, the Yellow River Delta wetlands have undergone rapid degradation due to water scarcity, pollution, and anthropogenic disturbance; the population fluctuations of the Oriental Ciconia boyciana, a keystone species, directly reflect breaches in ecological balance. Weber asserts that the traditional Chinese concept of “the unity of heaven and man”(tian ren he yi) regards humanity and nature as an indivisible whole, emphasizing moral self-discipline and harmonious coexistence (Weber, 2005). However, modern societal development has weakened this balance. Therefore, this study focuses on watercolor depictions of the Oriental Ciconia boyciana, which leverage its cultural status as a symbol of auspiciousness and utilize artistic expression to stimulate public ecological awareness and reverence for nature, thereby mobilizing support for wetland preservation.

During the preliminary sketching phase, artists abstract and simplify forms according to the chosen theme and subject. Rather than aiming for photographic replication, they distill objective imagery into geometric shapes—or even into fundamental elements such as points, lines, and planes. In doing so, they replace literal depiction

with a more subjective rendering of pictorial elements, thereby clarifying the boundary between reality and artistic interpretation.

Artworks that achieve recognition in art history must possess a unique allure, embodying the personal emotions of the artist. In the Flying Birds and New Glory watercolor series, the artist depicts natural landscapes from multiple perspectives, highlighting the ecological beauty of the Yellow River Delta Nature Reserve. In rendering the lush vegetation and the animated postures of frolicking the Ciconia boycianas, the paintings delicately portray the reserve’s vibrant vitality.

Composition Design

In the initial creative phase, the artist subjected the rectangular format to segmentation and collage, combining disparate scenes into a grand visual panorama. However, due to difficulties involved in managing large-scale scenes, scope of depiction was incrementally reduced after multiple iterations. Ultimately, three works were selected, each employing S-curve, circular, and diagonal compositions (Figure 8) to enhance visual expressiveness with more precise layouts, deepening the ecological theme and directing viewers’ attention to the Oriental Ciconia boyciana’s survival status and habitat conservation issues.

Series(a) Series(b) Series(c)
Figure 8: Sketches for the Flying Birds and New Glory Series.

In Series One, an elongated S-curve functions as the dominant visual vector, guiding the viewer’s eye from the lower-left foreground toward the upper-right background. The S-shaped configuration is purposefully employed for its capacity to evoke temporal progression and ecological immersion. Nine Ciconia boyciana are staggered along this

serpentine path, acting as a visual metronome whose alternating states of vigilance and repose intensify rhythmic perception. Concurrently, foliage gradually diminishes in scale along the curve, generating atmospheric perspective that deepens spatial recession and conjures associations with the winding waterways of an estuarine wetland.

In Series Two employs a circular schema: three out-stretched Oriental storks occupy the centre, encircled by flowing reeds and water that echo the ring. This closed loop draws the gaze inward, symbolising harmony, custodial reverence, and the conservation theme. The foliage's graded density forms a soft chiaroscuro halo, so the vegetal ring acts simultaneously as compositional anchor and metaphorical sanctuary, signalling the wetland's cyclical renewal.

In Series Three adopts a diagonal layout to convey instant momentum and direction. The two storks ride an upward diagonal that pulls the eye along their implied flight path, underscoring migration's urgency. Slanted reeds echo the vector yet vary in density, anchoring the scene so dynamism never dissolves into chaos. Thus, the diagonal simultaneously heightens narrative tension and preserves compositional balance, giving viewers a vivid sense of the wetland drama.

Figure 9: Completed Line Drawings and Detailed Drawings of the Flying Bird and New Glory Series.

The artist employs meticulous line work to transform the three-dimensional forms of the Oriental *Ciconia boyciana* and wetland vegetation into flattened, ornamentally and expressive planar constructions. Realistically rendering the storks' wings and body structures and weaving rhythmic motifs into the flowing water and reed background, the lines preserve a sense of spatial depth while enhancing both layering and narrative coherence. This approach fuses traditional painting's emphasis on line and structure with watercolor's inherent fluidity, striking a balance between realism and abstraction and using a clear compositional framework to underscore the theme of ecological conservation.

Color Design

In the initial color studies, the artist renders the river in a pale green that closely matches the stork's plumage, blurring the boundaries between subject and background and sacrificing hierarchical focus. Additionally, the artist employs overly saturated or vivid hues (Figure 10) that undermine the composition's overall harmony and aesthetic subtlety, rendering the work superficial and devoid of refined atmosphere.

To address this issue, the artist shifts the river's hue to pale blue, which increases the visual separation between subject and background and gives the images greater spatial depth. To reduce overall saturation in the final work (Figure 11), the artist

employs a muted gray palette anchored by blue-green tones, interspersing light and dark greens and warm accents of orange and pale yellow. The

juxtaposition and blending of cool and warm tones achieves chromatic balance, effectively elevating the work's textural quality.

Figure 10: Initial Color Study (Figure for Section 4.3).

Across the series, a light-wash technique forms the core of color application, leveraging watercolor's inherent transparency to produce a clear and refined visual effect. The purity, simplicity, and

poetic nuance emphasized by the light wash align seamlessly with the ecological ambiance sought by the works.

Figure 11: Final Work from the Flying Birds and New Glory Series.

CONCLUSION

Historically, painting has served as a consistent and indispensable cultural medium for artistic development across human civilizations. With its distinct philosophies and techniques, Chinese painting showcases national characteristics and aesthetic values, and its creative principles remain treasures of the art form. In particular, contemporary Chinese watercolor painting builds on Western techniques and integrates localized innovations to achieve an organic fusion of technique and expression.

By practically exploring Chinese watercolor painting and focusing on depictions of the Oriental Ciconia boyciana, this study elucidates the core value of this genre's artistic language in technique integration and aesthetic expression. It first reviewed the developmental trajectory and expressive techniques of Chinese watercolor painting, highlighting its inherent compatibility with traditional Chinese brush-and-ink painting, and analyzed its forms of expression while integrating the traditional aesthetic of "artistic conception." Considering diverse compositional structures and color languages, the study then revealed the unique emotional resonances inherent in Chinese watercolor. Finally, it presented specific creative works that demonstrate the dynamic beauty of the Yellow River Delta wetland ecosystem, subtly prompting viewers to reflect on the human–nature relationship while engaging with art.

Emphasizing the academic value of Chinese watercolor for ecological conservation advocacy and public environmental awareness enhancement, this study underscored the unique advantages and practical significance of merging traditional Chinese painting aesthetics with modern watercolor expression. Overall, this comprehensive exploration reveals technique integration and thematic creation as the dual bases of Chinese watercolor's artistic language. On the academic level, by showing how the integration of traditional Chinese painting aesthetics into the watercolor medium expanded the expressive boundaries of Chinese watercolor and enriched its linguistic system, this study highlights the scholarly value of this cross-cultural fusion. On a practical level, it validates the feasibility of employing artistic creation to serve ecological civilization: watercolor painting, as a contemporary art form, not only accentuates the beauty of nature but also inculcates social responsibility for environmental protection, offering an effective pathway for enhancing public environmental awareness.

Going forward, Chinese watercolor artists should continue to deepen and expand ecological narratives, cultural transmission, and visual innovation, pushing watercolor's transformation

from a mere vehicle of aesthetic experience into a powerful force for promoting ecological civilization and disseminating cultural values. At the policy level, tighter alignment with national and local "ecological-civilization" agendas would allow exhibitions, public-art commissions, and artist residencies to function as highly visible soft-power extensions of environmental legislation, thereby translating works on paper into concrete markers of policy implementation.

At the educational level, watercolor can function as an integrative teaching tool: students observe local ecosystems, embed field data in their sketches, and present the results in exhibition-seminars, thereby learning science, cultural history, and communication through the very act of painting.

In the context of environmental conservation, watercolor paintings employ chromatic nuance and symbolic imagery to render ecological crises tangible, eliciting viewers' resonance and reflection through aesthetic engagement and thereby activating both emotional and cognitive responses. This process fosters a transition from mere awareness to concrete actions—such as reducing plastic consumption, participating in waste segregation, or engaging in environmental volunteer initiatives—and ultimately cultivates enduring conservation impacts at the broader societal level.

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